

SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT LIQUID HYDROGEN TANKS USING MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION- MAKING METHODS

Aikaterini Anagnostopoulou¹, Konstantinos Tserpes², Dimitris Sotiropoulos², Georgios Lampeas⁴, J. Gonzalez-Teodoro⁵ and B. Carrasco Loras⁶

¹Laboratory of Technology & Strength of Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering & Aeronautics, University of Patras, Patras, Greece
Email: aikat.anagnostopoulou@ac.upatras.gr

²Laboratory of Technology & Strength of Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering & Aeronautics, University of Patras, Patras, Greece
Email: kitserpes@upatras.gr

³Department of Electrical Engineering, University of the Peloponnese, Patras, Greece
Email: dg.sotiropoulos@uop.gr

⁴Laboratory of Technology & Strength of Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering & Aeronautics, University of Patras, Patras, Greece
Email: lampeas@upatras.gr

⁵Aciturri Engineering, S.L.U. – Centro de Tres Cantos, Avda. de la Industria, 19 28760 – Tres Cantos, Madrid, Spain
Email: JorgeRafael.Gonzalez@aciturri.com

⁶Aciturri Engineering, S.L.U. – Centro de Tres Cantos, Avda. de la Industria, 19 28760 – Tres Cantos, Madrid, Spain
Email: Blanca.Carrasco@aciturri.com

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Abstract

In this paper, a cradle-to-gate, mathematically robust, sustainability assessment methodology for aircraft components is proposed. The assessment is made by applying the R-TOPSIS multi-criteria decision making method to nine different criteria which are categorized to environment, cost and performance. The environmental criteria are evaluated from a life cycle analysis and the cost criteria from a life cycle costing analysis. Both analyses are performed using the SimaPro software. The performance is assessed in terms of component's mass. The proposed methodology is used to assess the sustainability of novel composite liquid hydrogen storage tanks. Six different tank options are assessed; they differ in terms of the inner tank material (Aluminium-2219T8, PEI 20% CF, Stainless Steel AISI316). For the specific application, the criteria weights are derived using six different objective weighting methods. All weighting methods have resulted to the same most sustainable option but differ in the other options ranking, which highlights the importance of the criteria weights. A variation analysis conducted on the effects of the weights has revealed the criteria with the lowest and the highest significances and the highest uncertainty. The proposed methodology can be applied to any aircraft component, provided that the data required are available.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest on the environmental impact of the aviation sector. This sector is responsible for approximately 2.5% of global energy-related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, and also produces various non-carbon emissions that contribute to the radiative forcing of

the Earth's climate system [1], [2]. To substantially mitigate the environmental impacts of aviation and to align with the CO₂ benchmarks outlined in the Paris Agreement, as well as with the emission reduction targets outlined in the Flightpath 2050 [3], simple improvements to traditional aircraft technologies are not sufficient. In pursuit of this goal, rigorous testing of alternative fuels such as hydrogen, boasting zero emissions, alongside other biofuels or hybrid fuel solutions, is underway. These undertakings demand substantial modifications to aircraft infrastructure, including layout, storage, distribution systems, and materials required. Although emissions during the operational phase of aircraft comprise the predominant share [4], the significance of choices concerning material production and manufacturing techniques cannot be overlooked. Hence, it is imperative to precisely assess these impacts, in order to choose the most environmentally friendly option using holistic sustainability assessment methodologies. Until today, most sustainability assessments have been restrained to Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC). Numerous LCA and LCC studies have studied material selection [5], fuel options [6], and aircraft component manufacturing [7], seeking for environmentally advantageous solutions throughout production, utilization, and end-of-life stages. However, only a few works have contributed towards a more integrated sustainability assessment approach by combining different criteria. For instance, in [8], Markatos and Pantelakis have assessed and compared aircrafts under the prism of sustainable aviation using a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methodology, combining the analytic hierarchy process and an appropriate weighted addition model. One of the means for achieving a cleaner aviation is low-carbon propulsion technologies or alternative fuels, such as hydrogen. In the H2ELIOS project (<https://h2elios.eu/home>), within the frame of which the present work is conducted, innovative hydrogen storage solutions for aviation use are explored. The main aim is to develop lightweight and cost-effective solutions for storing liquid hydrogen. Sustainable, lightweight polymer-based materials for the tank structure will be used in combination with automated techniques for manufacturing to ensure close tolerances and high-quality finish.

In the present work, a sustainability assessment methodology for aircraft components is developed and applied to liquid hydrogen storage tanks. The methodology goes beyond LCA and LCC, is built upon a solid mathematical framework and designed so as to be easily integrated into an eco-design approach.

2. Technological problem

The tanks' structure comprises an inner and an outer tank, along with appropriate thermal insulation. Two main configurations are currently considered: Option A (Fig. 1(a)), and Option B (Fig. 1(b)); the difference between the two options lies on the outer tank. The outer tank is composed of a cylinder fabricated using the automated fiber placement process, along with two spherical caps produced via a hand lay-up process. Both the cylinder and caps are made of thermoset composite material. Silica aerogel insulation material is utilized for the outer insulation, while Polyisocyanurate is employed for the inner insulation. For the inner tank, three alternative materials/manufacturing processes are considered: (1) aluminum 2219T8 manufactured using deep drawing and friction stir welding, (2) stainless steel AISI 316 produced via deep drawing and friction stir welding, and (3) thermoplastic composite PEI with 20% wt CF manufactured through large format additive manufacturing. Alternating the three materials of the inner tank, six alternative tanks are developed as listed in Table 1.

3. The sustainability assessment methodology

3.1 Criteria

While the definition of sustainability remains fluid, it conventionally encompasses environmental, economic, technical and social facets. In the present study, the first three facets are considered.

3.1.1 Environmental criteria

The environmental criteria are based on a comprehensive cradle-to-gate LCA conducted using the SimaPro software (Ecoinvent 3 library) according to the ISO standards. LCA involves the following steps:

- Definition of goal and scope: This work aims to assess the environmental impact of liquid hydrogen storage tanks. The assessment considers various materials, geometries, and manufacturing processes employed in producing the six alternatives.
- Functional Unit: Production of each liquid hydrogen tank alternative.
- System boundaries: LCA focuses on the production of the materials and the manufacturing processes that were used for the production of the different parts of the tanks (cradle-to-gate analysis). Insulations were excluded from the analysis as they remain consistent across all alternatives, thus exerting no impact on the decision-making process among them. The transportation and final assembly processes were also excluded due to a lack of data.
- Data inventory: The primary source of data inventory used in the analysis was obtained from the Ecoinvent database, the H2ELIOS project, and the literature.

Figure 1. (a) Option A tank, (b) Option B tank

Table 1. Listing of the six alternative tanks.

Alternatives	Outer tank	Inner tank	Int. insulation	Ext. insulation
A1	A	Aluminium-2219T8	Silica aerogel	Polyisocyanurate
A2	A	PEI 20% CF	Silica aerogel	Polyisocyanurate
A3	A	Stainless Steel AISI316	Silica aerogel	Polyisocyanurate
B1	B	Aluminium-2219T8	Silica aerogel	Polyisocyanurate
B2	B	PEI 20% CF	Silica aerogel	Polyisocyanurate
B3	B	Stainless Steel AISI316	Silica aerogel	Polyisocyanurate

The environmental criteria were calculated using two methods: ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) V1.08 and IPCC 2021 GWP100 V1.02. The ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method in SimaPro [9] falls within the global category, indicating that its characterization factors are tailored to represent impacts on a global scale. This method is rooted in the Hierarchist perspective (H), aligning with widely accepted policy principles concerning time frame and other relevant issues. On the other hand, IPCC 2021 GWP100 belongs to the Single Issue category in SimaPro, providing results regarding Global Warming Potential (GWP) measured in kg of CO₂ equivalent. The environmental criteria used (C1 to C4) are described in Table 2. Human Health is quantified as the combined years of life lost and years lived with disability, represented as Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs). Ecosystems are assessed in terms of species loss over a defined area and time period. Resource scarcity is measured as the additional costs of future resource production over an infinite timeframe, assuming constant annual production and applying a 3% discount rate [9].

3.1.2 Cost criteria

LCC is a method of economic analysis directed at all costs related to constructing, operating, and maintaining a construction project over a defined period [10]. An LCC methodology is established

within SimaPro to encompass all expenses associated with tank production. The cost criteria C5 to C8 are described in Table 2. The Material cost comprises expenditures on raw materials utilized (Aluminum 2219T8, Stainless Steel AISI316, PEI 20% CF), while the Personnel cost accounts for labor across various project stages (LFAM, AFP, Hand Layup, Deep Drawing processes). The Energy cost encompasses energy consumption during production and manufacturing processes, while the Service cost encapsulates equipment rental expenses necessary for manufacturing processes.

Table 2 presents the criteria used in the MCDM method to assess the sustainability of composite aircraft liquid hydrogen tanks. Each criterion is categorized based on its primary impact on the environment, cost, or performance. All criteria are considered cost attributes, where a lower value is preferable. The "Cost" impact type indicates that a lower criterion value is preferred, contributing to a higher sustainability ranking of the aircraft tank.

Table 2. Criteria descriptions and categories for MCDM analysis.

Criteria	Description	Category	Impact Type
C1	Human Health (DALY's)	Environment	Cost
C2	Ecosystems (species.year)	Environment	Cost
C3	Resources (USD 2013)	Environment	Cost
C4	Global Warming Potential (kg CO ₂)	Environment	Cost
C5	Personnel Cost	Cost	Cost
C6	Material Cost	Cost	Cost
C7	Energy Cost	Cost	Cost
C8	Service Cost	Cost	Cost
C9	Mass	Performance	Cost

3.1.3 Performance criterion

The mass of the entire tank is designated as the performance criterion C9, as it is linked to the values utilized in sustainability assessments: a lighter tank necessitates less material, energy, and cost and, consequently, emits fewer associated emissions. Furthermore, a lighter tank enhances aircraft efficiency by reducing fuel consumption throughout the operational phase.

3.2 The R-TOPSIS method for sustainable decision-making

The sustainability of tanks is assessed using the R-TOPSIS method, introduced by Aires and Ferreira [11]. This method is a variant of the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), which stands as one of the most widely employed approaches in MCDM [10]. The foundational principle of TOPSIS is that the optimal alternative should be the closest to the positive ideal solution (PIS) and the farthest from the negative ideal solution (NIS). However, traditional TOPSIS can be susceptible to the Rank Reversal Problem (RRP), where the introduction or removal of alternatives can unexpectedly alter the rankings of the remaining options. R-TOPSIS addresses this issue by modifying the approach to stabilize rankings despite alternative changes [11]. This enhancement makes R-TOPSIS particularly valuable for providing robust insights into optimal decision-making by ensuring that its sustainability rankings are consistent and reliable, even as assessment conditions vary. The algorithm for R-TOPSIS is implemented as follows [11]:

Step 1: Define a set of alternatives $(A = [a_i]_m)$;

Step 2: Define a set of criteria $(C = [c_j]_n)$, as well as a subdomain of real numbers $D = [d_j]_{2 \times n}$,

where $d_j \in \mathbb{R}$ to evaluate the rating of the alternatives, where d_{1j} is the minimum value of D_j and d_{2j} is the maximum value of D_j .

Step 3: Estimate the performance rating of the alternatives as $X = [x_{ij}]_{m \times n}$;

Step 4: Elicit the criteria weights as $W = [w_j]_n$, where $w_j > 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$;

Step 5: Calculate the normalized decision matrix (n_{ij}) by using Max or Max-Min as: Step 5.1: Max

$$n_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{d_{2j}}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Step 5.2: Max-Min

$$n_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - d_{ij}}{d_{2j} - d_{1j}}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Step 6: Calculate the weighted normalized decision matrix (r_{ij}) as:

$$r_{ij} = w_j \times n_{ij}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Step 7: Set the negative (NIS) and positive (PIS) ideal solutions as:

$$\text{NIS} = \{r_1^-, \dots, r_n^-\}, \quad \text{where } r_j^- = \frac{d_{1j}}{d_{2j}} w_j \text{ if } j \in B \text{ and } r_j^- = w_j \text{ if } j \in C$$

$$\text{PIS} = \{r_1^+, \dots, r_n^+\}, \quad \text{where } r_j^+ = w_j \text{ if } j \in B \text{ and } r_j^+ = \frac{d_{1j}}{d_{2j}} w_j \text{ if } j \in C$$

Step 8: Calculate the distances of each alternative i to the ideal solutions as:

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} - r_j^+)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; \quad S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (r_{ij} - r_j^-)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Step 9: Calculate the closeness coefficient of the alternatives (CC_i) as:

$$CC_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-}$$

It is evident from the formulation of the closeness coefficient (CC_i) constrained between 0 and 1. As CC_i approaches the upper limit of this range, the value S_i^+ must tend toward 0, implying proximity to the positive ideal solution (PIS). Therefore, a higher CC_i value denotes that an alternative is more aligned with the PIS and thus more desirable. Consequently, alternatives are ranked in descending order based on their CC_i values, with the highest CC_i reflecting the most favorable option in the given decision-making scenario.

3.3 Objective weighting methods

The assignment of weights in multiple criteria problems is a crucial stage in decision-making. Depending on the problem and the specialist analyzing it, the significance of criteria varies from case to case. Both subjective and objective methods are employed to determine the criteria weights. In sustainability assessment, which encompasses criteria from various domains, subjective weighting methods require input from multiple specialists to ensure accuracy and a well-rounded understanding of the criteria's importance. However, this paper does not explore subjective weighting methods due to the need for many specialists and the diversity of their expertise. Instead, it adopts six distinct objective weighting methods: the Standard Deviation (SD) method, the Coefficient of Variance (COV) method, the CRITIC method [11], the Entropy method, the MEREC method [12], and an integrated approach combining the CRITIC and Entropy methods [11]. Following the determination of weights through these objective methods, the R-TOPSIS technique [13] is employed to integrate these weights into the decision-making framework.

4. Results

All mentioned objective weighting methods and the R-TOPSIS algorithm have been implemented in MATLAB (R2024a) to analyze the decision matrix and derive the criteria weights, facilitating a comprehensive evaluation of alternative sustainability practices.

4.1 Construction of the Sustainability Decision Matrix

Following the methodology outlined in Section 3, a decision matrix has been formulated using data generated by SimaPro, as illustrated in Table 3. All criteria are classified as cost, emphasizing the preference for lower values. More specifically, criteria C1 through C4 are associated with environmental factors, underscoring their importance in ecological assessments. In contrast, criteria C5 to C8 are linked to economic aspects, reflecting the financial impacts. Additionally, criterion C9 is designated as a performance criterion, highlighting its role in evaluating the overall efficiency of the assessed solutions.

Table 3. Decision matrix.

Alternatives	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9
A1	0.0246	4.78E-05	601	9740	713	12600	5640	1570	106.4976
A2	0.0212	4.18E-05	510	8310	924	13700	5410	1750	78.3891
A3	0.0198	3.96E-05	567	8020	713	12500	5620	1570	198.6931
B1	0.0181	3.50E-05	457	7240	533	8700	3910	1570	94.4948
B2	0.0147	2.91E-05	366	5810	744	9850	3670	1750	66.3862
B3	0.0134	2.68E-05	423	5520	533	8680	3890	1570	186.6903

4.2 Criteria weights analysis

In the context of MCDM methods, "importance" refers to the weight assigned to a criterion; the higher the weight assigned to a criterion, the greater its importance is. However, analyzing the variation across different objective weighting methods can also provide valuable insights regarding which criteria are consistently considered important or unimportant and which criteria have a higher level of agreement among methods.

Table 4 summarizes the statistical analysis performed on the weights of nine criteria (C1 through C9) derived from the six (6) objective weighting methods. Each row corresponds to a statistical measure, including mean (Mean), standard deviation (Std), coefficient of variation (CV), minimum (Min), maximum (Max), and range (Range) of the weights assigned to each criterion. The mean values offer insights into the relative importance assigned to each criterion across the objective methods. Criterion C9, with the highest mean weight of 0.2965, is identified as the most critical factor in the decision-making process. The standard deviation quantifies the consensus or divergence among the methods, with C9 showing the highest standard deviation of 0.0852, indicating substantial disagreement among the methods on its importance. The minimum and maximum weights represent the bounds of the weights assigned by the methods, with the range indicating the extent of variability for each criterion. The weight range for each criterion indicates the extent of disagreement among the methods. A more extensive range indicates a more significant discrepancy in how different methods assess the importance of a criterion. For instance, C9 exhibits the widest range of 0.2106, notably more critical than the others, indicating a very high level of disagreement. At the same time, C3 has a relatively more minor range, indicating more consistency in evaluating its importance. In contrast, C8 shows the lowest mean weight of 0.0414 and the highest standard deviation relative to its mean, 0.6527, highlighting it as the least critical but most uncertain criterion. This statistical overview helps us understand the robustness and sensitivity of the overall MCDM analysis to the choice of weighting method, with broader implications for the reliability of the derived rankings.

Table 4. Variation in criteria weights across various objective weighting methods.

C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9
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Mean	0.1026	0.0978	0.0831	0.0987	0.1104	0.0857	0.0839	0.0414	0.2965
Std	0.0151	0.0159	0.0127	0.0146	0.0157	0.0175	0.0216	0.0270	0.0852
CV	0.1474	0.1624	0.1532	0.1480	0.1425	0.2042	0.2573	0.6527	0.2872
Min	0.0807	0.0761	0.0652	0.0784	0.0865	0.0673	0.0566	0.0062	0.1934
Max	0.1183	0.1128	0.1003	0.1141	0.1309	0.1086	0.1150	0.0798	0.4040
Range	0.0375	0.0367	0.0351	0.0356	0.0443	0.0414	0.0584	0.0736	0.2106

4.3 Ranking

Table 5 lists the ranking of the six alternative tanks performed using the R-TOPSIS for the six weighting methods. The table shows that the B2 tank is consistently identified as the more sustainable option from all weighting methods. However, it is also important to mention that apart from the first option, the following options vary across the different weighting methods, highlighting the sensitivity of the ranking outcome to the objective weighting method assigned to the criteria. Despite these differences, tank B2 consistently appears as the top-ranked option across all methods, emphasizing its robust positioning as the most sustainable choice.

Table 5. Comparative R-TOPSIS rankings of tank options based on six objective weighting methods.

Ranking	SD	COV	Entropy	CRITIC	CRITIC-Entropy	MEREC
1	B2	B2	B2	B2	B2	B2
2	B1	B1	A2	A2	B1	B1
3	B3	A2	B1	B1	A2	A2
4	A2	B3	A1	A1	A1	B3
5	A1	A1	B3	B3	B3	A1
6	A3	A3	A3	A3	A3	A3

Following the assessment using various objective weighting methods, we employed the mean weights from Table 4 to conduct a ranking using R-TOPSIS. The results are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Rankings results using mean weights

Tanks	Scores	Ranks
B2	0.52078	1
B1	0.43395	2
A2	0.40939	3
A1	0.32605	4
B3	0.24418	5
A3	0.10113	6

Upon comparing the findings shown in Tables 5 and 6, both tables confirm the superiority of B2, underscoring its sustainability irrespective of the weighting methodology applied. While individual weighting methods show some rank shifts among the tanks, particularly for positions 2 through 6, mean weights aggregate these perspectives into one score, reducing the impact of method-specific biases.

5. Conclusions

In the present paper, we have proposed a sustainability assessment methodology for aircraft components. The methodology is based on nine criteria (4 related to environment, 4 related to cost and 1 related to performance), which are evaluated using the R-TOPSIS MCDM method. The methodology was applied to composite liquid hydrogen storage tanks designed for aerospace applications. For the specific application, the weights of the criteria were derived using 6 different objective weighting methods. Six alternative tanks originated from two main options were assessed. All weighting methods have indicated

that the alternative B2: Option B, Inner tank: PEI 20% CF, Internal insulation: Silica aerogel, External insulation: Polyisocyanurate as the more sustainable. The fact that all weighting methods have given the same winner enhances the robustness of the assessment. To understand the effects of weights on the ranking of the tanks fully, a variation analysis was conducted. The results show that there is a disagreement among the weighting methods on the significance of the Performance criterion (mass). On the other hand, there is an agreement on the significance of the Resources environmental criterion. Finally, the Service cost criterion has revealed to be the least critical but most uncertain criterion. The sustainability assessment methodology can be applied to any aircraft component and is considered to be the first but independent step towards the development of an integrated eco-design approach.

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